

LINKING FINANCIAL INCLUSION ON THE BUSINESS PERFORMANCE: THE CASE OF MICRO AND SMALL ENTERPRISES

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 23

Issue 9

Pages: 1190-1197

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2223

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13337277

Manuscript Accepted: 07-20-2024

Linking Financial Inclusion on the Business Performance: The Case of Micro and Small Enterprises

Sarah Jane B. Orillosa,* Camille George R. Olarte, Hana Khrystelle A. Cariño, Christ Stephen C. Halog, Allea Angelica N. Chua, Justine Noel L. Dasas, Jerome C. Orillosa

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study was conducted to determine the relationship and influence of financial inclusion on the business performance of micro and small enterprises (MSEs). The level of financial inclusion was investigated through access, usage, quality, and welfare. Business performance with its dimensions of sales growth, capital growth, labor increase, market growth and profit growth were also examined. Consequently, the relationship between financial inclusion and business performance, and the influence of financial inclusion on the business performance of MSEs were studied. Descriptive-correlational design was used to explore and describe connections between financial inclusion and business performance. Data were collected from the fifty (50) owners and managers of MSEs using stratified random sampling technique. Upon careful analysis of the results, it became evident that micro and small enterprises demonstrate a very high level of financial inclusion, coupled also with high results of their business performance. Further, it is found that there exists a statistically significant and positive relationship between financial inclusion and business performance. Moreover, it was revealed that financial inclusion significantly influences the business performance of MSEs. These findings underscore the critical importance of enhancing the financial inclusion initiatives for MSEs as it directly impacts and improves their overall business performance.

Keywords: *financial inclusion, business performance, micro and small enterprises*

Introduction

The challenges that affect the business performance of micro and small enterprises (MSEs) can be attributed to accessing affordable financing, navigating regulatory complexities and competing in an increasingly digital marketplace. In the context of MSEs, there is a number of challenges related to access to financial resources which translate to impediments in enterprise growth (Mutantabowa, 2018). The difficulty in obtaining formal financial services such as credit, insurance, and savings accounts often impedes the sustainable growth and success of MSEs as stated by Beck (2016).

In sub-Saharan Africa, MSEs have a harder time obtaining formal outside financing and have to deal with bigger problems as they try to grow (Lakuma et al., 2019). Oke et al. (2023) also demonstrated that MSEs in Nigeria have underperformed due to a combination of constraints such as limited financial access, unfavorable external conditions, and insufficient managerial abilities, among others.

The study of Suryani et al. (2015) highlighted that numerous micro and small enterprises (MSEs) face challenges in accessing banks due to the distant location of these financial institutions from their places of business. Similarly, Aritonang et al. (2023) showed that MSEs continue to face challenges in accessing capital, particularly credit from banks. Also, Opperman (2023) argued that microenterprises, which lack collateral, credit histories, and relationships, will have to depend on their insufficient funds if they do not have access to an inclusive financial system. This could be a significant barrier to the expansion and progress of MSE's effectiveness, especially due to the cautiousness of formal financial institutions in granting loans to business owners.

The Department of Trade and Industry's MSME Development Plan of 2017-2022 provided that one of the obstacles encountered by Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in the Philippines is the difficulty in obtaining financial resources (Lim et al., 2020). Generally, Philippine MSEs, especially micro businesses, often avoid commercial banks due to inaccessible terms, including high interest rates, minimum loan requirements, strict documentation, lengthy processing, short repayment periods, and limited access in rural areas. These barriers have substantial implications for the business performance of Philippine MSEs (Raquiza, 2021).

Despite the substantial progress in understanding the link between financial inclusion and business performance, there were limited local research studies conducted which motivated researchers to undertake the study. This research is significant as it aims to fill a critical knowledge gap by exploring the dynamics between financial inclusion and business performance of MSEs, thereby enriching the limited existing literature in the Philippines.

Research Questions

This study aimed to examine the effects and relationship of financial inclusion on the business performance of micro and small enterprises (MSEs). Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of MSEs in relation to number of years of operation, asset size, and number of employees?
2. What is the level of financial inclusion in terms of access, use, quality, and welfare of MSEs?
3. What is the level of business performance in terms of sales growth, capital growth, labor increase, market growth, and profit growth of MSEs?

4. Is there a significant relationship between financial inclusion and business performance of MSEs?

Literature Review

Financial Inclusion

Financial inclusion refers to the collective efforts to eliminate any obstacles that prevent the general public from accessing and utilizing financial services (Barajas et al., 2020). With the presence of this, access to financial services can significantly enhance the well-being of various enterprises due to the provision of formal financial services, such as savings, credit, payment facilities, and other goods to them (Irman et al., 2021). MSEs have a harder time obtaining formal outside financing and have to deal with bigger problems as they try to grow (Lakuma et al., 2019).

The study of Suryani et al. (2015) highlighted that numerous micro and small enterprises (MSEs) face challenges in accessing banks due to the distant location of these financial institutions from their places of business. Thus, Abor et al. (2020) emphasized that microenterprises which have financial resources can enhance the quality of their human capital, which is crucial for stimulating innovation and entrepreneurship in the economy. In addition, they explained that financial inclusion will empower them to preserve funds for their business, effectively handle potential risks, establish credit history, and have access to lending facilities. Gammage et al. (2017) provided additional evidence that improved financial inclusion can serve as a fundamental catalyst for enhancing the performance of micro and small enterprises (MSEs) and fostering economic growth.

Access. Access to finance is characterized as the capacity of individuals, households, business owners, and companies to get and make use of diverse financial services, should they want to do so (Adomako et al., 2016). The study conducted by Maravelle and Pandiella (2022) uncovered that having access to finance enhances financial inclusion and fosters the expansion of the financial sector, ultimately leading to overall economic growth. Nevertheless, there are certain obstacles associated with obtaining financial resources that result in hindrances to the expansion of enterprises (Mutantabowa, 2018). The micro and small enterprises (MSEs) that wanted to apply for credit is hindered by the constraints of guarantees requested by the bank, with the MSEs inability to pledge acceptable collateral as the common cause. Opperman (2023) argued that microenterprises, which lack collateral, credit histories, and relationships, will have to depend on their insufficient funds if they do not have access to an inclusive financial system. Lumenta and Worang (2019) pointed out that the accessibility of financial resources significantly influences the performance of these enterprises.

Usage. A truly inclusive financial system must prioritize and promote the utilization of its services by society's most vulnerable groups, specifically those who are impacted by barriers to financial inclusion (Camara & Tuesta, 2014). A study conducted by Centobelli et al. (2021) claimed that micro and small enterprises (MSEs) utilize financial resources to initiate and expand their activities, innovate new products, and make investments in human resources or manufacturing facilities. Similarly, Hutabarat (2018) demonstrated that those with greater financial literacy exhibit increased levels of usage, utilization, and comprehension of financial products and services. This is corroborated by the research conducted by Xiao et al. (2022), which showed that businesses prioritize the results of their financial capacity and strategically employ financial solutions that are in line with their specific needs.

Quality. Quality dimension evaluates the extent to which financial services efficiently cater to the demands and requirements of the customers (Banerjee et al., 2022). The dimension of financial inclusion encompasses not only access, but also the reliability, affordability, and suitability of financial services for micro and small enterprises (MSEs). Furthermore, Banerjee et al. (2022) highlighted that the capacity of financial services to fulfill the requirements and desires of their customers serves as a measure of excellence. For instance, Zigraiova and Tomas (2015) stated that the progress in technology, including the widespread use of mobile banking and digital financial services, has greatly enhanced the standard of financial services accessible to MSEs. These advancements provide ease and efficiency in terms of cost.

Welfare. The inclusion of enterprises in the financial sector can yield favorable outcomes for their welfare, as it grants them the opportunity to avail themselves of financial products and services that facilitate their expansion and achievement (Wijaya & Hartini, 2022). Further, Cole et al. (2013) highlighted that insurance products provide protection for micro and small enterprises (MSEs) against a range of risks, such as natural catastrophes, illness, and market volatility. The provision of insurance not only serves as a safeguard for the assets and livelihoods of MSEs, but also contributes to the enhancement of their general well-being. However, Aritonang et al. (2023) showed that MSEs in Indonesia continue to face challenges in accessing capital, particularly credit from banks. The proportion of loans allocated to MSEs is quite low compared to the total amount of loans distributed, with commercial banks experiencing a lack of growth, while rural banks are witnessing a decrease in lending to MSEs. Lekhanya (2016) provided further evidence that the insufficient funding hinders the ability of MSEs to thrive and expand.

Business Performance

Micro and small enterprises (MSEs) are recognized as successful strategies for boosting the country's gross domestic development, reducing unemployment, and creating favorable economic conditions (Kassa, 2021). However, inadequate access to financial services and financial constraints frequently impedes their efficacy and sustainability. Pomeroy et al. (2020) investigated the barriers to small-scale enterprise financial inclusion and found that access to formal financial services, also known as financial inclusion, can improve the financial resilience of small businesses. Moreover, Tambunan et al. (2022) emphasized that access to finance is an external factor

that affects the performance of MSEs. It can assist proprietors of MSEs in optimizing their operations by incorporating new products or boosting the production of the business.

Sales Growth. Covin et al. (2013) define the measurement of company's sales growth as the average rate of increase in sales revenue over the past three years. In this regard, Atnafu and Balda (2018) stated that effective inventory management is crucial for businesses as it is tailored to minimize expenses or maximize profits while meeting customer demands. Consequently, Ton and Raman (2015) explained that the presence of a larger variety of products within a store enhances the likelihood that customers will successfully acquire the items they need. The inventory of merchandise for specific products not only improves service standards, but also stimulates customer demand, resulting in increased sales. Thus, Cavalchire (2023) emphasized the importance of establishing and nurturing positive relationships with banks to secure substantial amounts of credit, particularly for small-scale enterprises.

Capital Growth. In their study, Marchese and de la Chaux (2022) elucidated that financial inclusion serves as a primary mechanism for obtaining business capital for micro and small firms. In the research conducted by Adiandari and Winata (2020), the incorporation of financial services has been noted to play a crucial role in improving the performance of Micro and Small Enterprises (MSEs). The main reason for this is that financial inclusion enables MSEs to easily access credit and financing options provided by banks. On the other hand, Bhaskar (2013) found that financial institutions experienced a higher rate of credit growth for the past years. The provision of essential financial services to micro and small businesses is facilitated by them, which include loans, savings, money transfer services, and micro-insurance.

Labor Increase. Ananda and Susilowati (2017) highlighted that micro and small enterprises (MSEs) are characterized by their labor-intensive characteristics and lack of stringent standards in terms of education levels, worker experience, and company capital. The research of Fiala (2015) suggested that enterprises with greater access to financial resources have the potential to allocate investments towards the recruitment of highly trained and motivated personnel, implementation of training programs, and the execution of initiatives aimed at fostering trust among employees. Thus, a business with access to finance can provide the necessary financial resources to recruit and retain skilled personnel, enabling the business to meet increasing demand and sustain growth (Fundid, 2023).

Market Growth. Adelino et al. (2017) specified that businesses with more access to financing have a higher chance of succeeding and expanding more quickly. Micro enterprises can effectively mitigate risk, accumulate funds for their business, develop credit records, and avail credit facilities by utilizing and having access to financial services. The enhancement in economic resilience has the capacity to result in a more stable macroeconomic environment that is conducive to economic expansion (Abor et al., 2020). Contrastingly, the study of Overman (2016) emphasized that many entrepreneurs and enterprises may lack a comprehensive understanding of the potential advantages of securing financial resources or their probable likelihood of obtaining such resources, so impeding the market expansion their businesses.

Profit Growth. Profitability refers to the capacity of a company to earn profits in relation to its sales and investment (Indra et al., 2020). Moreover, a research by Dewinta and Setiawan (2016) explained that the profitability pertains to a company's capacity to earn profits within a specific period, considering its level of sales, assets, and capital. Consequently, Ngoc et al. (2021) highlighted the significance of finance for Micro and Small Enterprises (MSEs) as it directly influences the business's worth and the owners' capacity to increase their earnings. Oke et al. (2023) also showed that providing MSEs with financial resources will improve their profitability and efficiency, mitigate liquidity concerns, and increase the quality of their assets.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive-correlational research design. The purpose of a descriptive-correlational research design is to identify and explain the relationships between variables (Stangor, 2024). Specifically, Siedlecki (2020) characterized descriptive research as a study design that methodically collects data to describe and analyze a phenomenon, situation, or population under investigation. In contrast, a correlational research design examines correlations between variables without requiring the researcher to alter or modify any of them (Bhandari, 2023).

This study is descriptive because it described the level of financial inclusion in terms of access, usage, quality, and welfare, as well as the level of business performance concerning sales growth, capital growth, labor increases, market growth, and profit growth. Furthermore, it is correlational because it investigated the relationship between financial inclusion and business performance of MSEs.

Respondents

This research was carried out in the first district of Cotabato province, Philippines, with an area of concentration in the municipalities of Pigcawayan, Alamada, Libungan, Midsayap, and Aleosan (PALMA). To ensure equitable representation of these areas, ten (10) respondents from each municipality resulting in fifty (50) respondents in total were selected to assess the relationship of financial inclusion on the business performance of micro and small enterprises (MSEs). The survey involved business owners and managers from the aforementioned municipalities of different MSEs.

Instruments

The study used an adapted questionnaire from Aritonang et al. (2023) with minor modifications. The questionnaire is composed of three (3) parts. The first part is the demographic profile of the MSE sector, which consists of business name, number of years of operation, asset size, and number of employees. The second part of the questionnaire assessed the level of financial inclusion with regard to the access, usage, quality, and welfare of MSEs. The third part of the questionnaire is about the MSEs' business performance, with indicators such as sales growth, capital growth, labor increases, market growth, and profit growth.

In the second and third portions of the questionnaire, the Likert scale was utilized to identify the responses that most closely correspond to the perspectives of the participants concerning the indicators. The assessment comprised a set of five (5) options, with each question presented as a declarative statement. Participants have the option to express their level of agreement or disagreement towards the statements using a scale from Strongly Agree (5), Agree (4), Moderately Agree (3), Disagree (2), and Strongly Disagree (1). To ensure face validity, expert judgments from the validators were sought during the modification process. The adapted instrument had been subjected to Cronbach's Alpha reliability test, where all instruments have demonstrated reliability, as evidenced by their overall Cronbach's alpha value which is "0.70". Thus, the instrument is deemed reliable.

Procedure

This study used a survey questionnaire method to collect the primary data. Prior to commencing the study, the researchers obtained the necessary approval from the Dean of the College of Business and Accountancy. Subsequently, following approval from the Dean, the researchers formally requested participation from the owners or managers of the micro and small enterprises (MSEs) through a letter jointly signed by the researchers and endorsed by their adviser.

Upon securing the consent of the authorized persons of MSEs, the researchers proceeded to distribute the questionnaires to the selected respondents. To accommodate the busy schedules and operational demands of the respondents, a generous timeframe was allocated for the completion of the survey questionnaire. Once all the questionnaires had been collected, the data was promptly handed over to a qualified statistician for the tallying and subsequent analysis, employing appropriate statistical tools and methodologies.

Ethical Considerations

The questionnaire utilized in the survey is adapted from Aritonang et al. (2023) which undergone minor adjustments to suit the context of the study. The adapted instrument has passed through a comprehensive assessment from the research adviser and validators to ensure face and content validity. Moreover, the Cronbach's Alpha of the original instrument indicated a result of 0.70 which means that the instrument is reliable. Additionally, no personal names or enterprise identities were included in the presentation and discussion of data. All information provided by the respondents were treated with the utmost confidentiality, adhering to ethical research standards and respecting the participants' right to privacy.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the result and findings of the study. The results are presented in tabular forms.

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Table 1 presents the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of number of years of operation, asset size, and number of employees.

Table 1. Demographic Profile of the Respondents

<i>Profile of the Respondents</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Years of Business Operation		
1 - 5 years	17	34
6 - 10 years	9	18
10 years and above	24	48
Total	50	100
Asset Size		
Up to Php 3,000,000	29	58
Php 3,000,001 - Php 15,000,000	21	42
Total	50	100
Number of Employees		
1 - 9 employees	39	78
10 - 99 employees	11	22
Total	50	100

The data illustrated in Table 1 that the highest frequency is observed within the group of enterprises who have been operating for 10 years and above which represents twenty-four (24) or forty-eight percent (48%) out of fifty (50) business enterprises. On the contrary, the lowest frequency is observed among those who have been in business operation for 6 to 10 years, accounting for nine (9) business enterprises or eighteen percent (18%) out of fifty (50) total respondents. In terms of asset size, most of the respondents are micro

enterprises with assets ranging from Php. 1 to Php. 3,000,000, containing twenty-nine (29) or fifty-eight percent (58%) of the fifty (50) total business enterprises. On the other hand, the rest of the respondents are small enterprises with assets ranging from Php. 3,000,001 to Php. 15,000,000 which represents twenty-one (21) or forty-two percent (42%) of the fifty (50) total respondents. Lastly, in terms of the number of employees, the highest frequency is found within the group of enterprises with 1 to 9 employees, representing thirty-nine (39) or seventy-eight percent (78%) of the total business respondents. Conversely, the category with the lowest frequency is the enterprises with 10 to 99 employees, comprising eleven (11) or twenty-two (22%) of the total respondents.

Level of Financial Inclusion

Table 2 presents the data on the level of financial inclusion in terms of access, usage, quality, and welfare. The results show quality as the highest indicator rated as Strongly Agree with an overall mean of 4.44 and a standard deviation of 0.69. On the contrary, the lowest indicator is welfare rated as Agree with an overall mean of 4.07 and a standard deviation of 1.09. With these figures, the level of financial inclusion in micro and small enterprises (MSEs) is rated as Strongly Agree with a grand mean of 4.30 and an average standard deviation of 0.88.

Table 2. *Level of Financial Inclusion*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
Access	4.39	0.81	Strongly Agree	Very High
Usage	4.29	0.86	Strongly Agree	Very High
Quality	4.44	0.69	Strongly Agree	Very High
Welfare	4.07	1.09	Agree	High
Grand Mean	4.30		Strongly Agree	Very High
Average Standard Deviation		0.88		

Level of Business Performance

Table 3 shows the data on the level of business performance in terms of sales growth, capital growth, labor increase, market growth, and profit growth. The results reveal that the profit growth indicator obtained the highest overall mean of 4.27 with a standard deviation of 0.85 and a description of Strongly Agree. Conversely, the indicator labor increased garnered the lowest overall mean of 3.76 with a standard deviation of 1.11 and a description of Agree. Overall, the level of business performance is rated as Agree with a grand mean of 3.98 and an average standard deviation of 1.00.

Table 3. *Level of Business Performance*

Summary	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
Sales Growth	4.05	0.91	Agree	High
Capital Growth	3.79	1.05	Agree	High
Labor Increase	3.76	1.11	Agree	High
Market Growth	4.09	0.98	Agree	High
Profit Growth	4.27	0.85	Strongly Agree	Very High
Grand Mean	3.98		Agree	High
Average Standard Deviation		1.00		

Relationship Between Financial Inclusion and Business Performance

Table 4 presents the data on the relationship between financial inclusion and business performance of MSEs using Spearman rank correlation. It can be observed that there exists a statistically significant and positive correlation ($r = 0.388$) between the variables financial inclusion and business performance at a significance level of 0.05 (two-tailed). This suggests a positive relationship between financial inclusion and business performance, indicating that as the independent variable increases, the dependent variable tends to improve. This correlation is unlikely to be attributed to random chance.

Table 4. *Relationship Between Financial Inclusion and Business Performance*

Variables	N	df	r-value	p-value	Indication	Decision
Financial Inclusion	50	49	0.388	.005	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Business Performance						

Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Based on the frequency and percentage distributions, majority of the enterprises have been in operation for ten (10) years and above, with assets totaling up to Php. 3,000,000, and employing 1 to 9 individuals.

In general, the level of financial inclusion in the micro and small enterprises (MSEs) sector is very high. The findings indicate that there is a significant level of accessibility to financial products and services. This suggests that financial information and the availability of financial service providers are highly accessible and favorable. When it comes to the usage aspect, the results showed a very high level of utility of financial products and services among MSEs due to their active utilization of financial instruments in their business operations and using these according to their financial capabilities. Moreover, the said products and services exhibit a very high degree of quality because of the simplicity of their procedures and suitability to the needs of MSEs. Lastly, in the welfare dimension of financial inclusion, the results showed a high degree of wellness among MSEs, showing improvements in their business progress and

sustainability.

Furthermore, the level of business performance of MSEs is high in general. When it comes to its sales growth, results showed a high degree of growth in relation to sales or business turnover, production of merchandise, and the amount of demand for relative products. In the capital growth aspect, MSEs also exhibit a high degree of growth, particularly when it comes to the business assets, number of loans or financing provided by financial services institutions, and number of merchandise inventory. Moreover, the labor increase growth of MSEs is high, with particular emphasis on the number of interested employees and the number of workers employed in the business. The market growth aspect also exhibits a high level of progress concerning the number of new customers and expansion of business marketing. In the profit growth dimension of business performance, the results demonstrated a very high growth, especially in the context of profit and personal wealth of the enterprise.

After careful examination of the data, it has been established that there is a statistically significant and positive relationship between financial inclusion and business performance. The results also indicated that the degree of financial inclusion significantly affects the operational effectiveness of micro and small enterprises (MSEs). Thus, a significant degree of financial inclusion, encompassing access, usage, quality, and welfare, might enhance the business performance of MSEs in the aspect of sales growth, capital growth, labor increase, market growth, and profit growth.

Conclusions

Based on the study's findings, several key conclusions can be drawn. First, a significant proportion of the surveyed enterprises have been operating for ten (10) years and above, with the majority categorized as micro enterprises. Recognizing that the majority of surveyed enterprises fall within the micro enterprise category, there is still a need for specific policies and support mechanisms to be put in place to address the unique challenges and opportunities these businesses face. Second, the level of financial inclusion within the micro and small enterprises (MSEs) sector is very high, particularly in terms of access, usage, and the quality of financial services. This signifies that MSEs can easily access high quality financial products and services that are tailored to their specific needs. Third, the level of business performance of MSEs is generally high, with the profit growth dimension exhibiting a very high level of growth. Consequently, it may be inferred that MSEs are exhibiting satisfactory overall performance. They are not only sustaining their business but also enhancing their profitability. Moreover, the findings of the study validate a substantial and favorable correlation between financial inclusion and the business performance of MSEs. Therefore, it is advisable for policymakers and financial institutions to persist in their endeavors to improve financial inclusion.

The results of this study are limited to the specific sector context within the designated time frame. Thus, the selected municipalities may not fully represent the broader regional or national context and the findings may not capture the full spectrum of perspectives within the micro and small enterprise (MSEs) sector. While the study provides valuable insights, caution should be exercised when attempting to generalize these findings to a wider context.

References

- Adomako, S., Danso, A., & Ofori Damoah, J. (2016). The moderating influence of financial. *Venture Capital*, 18(1), 43-61.
- Abor, J., Adjasi, C., & Lensink, R. (2020). *Contemporary Issues in Development Finance*. London: Routledge. Retrieved from Routledge, Taylor, and Francis Group: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429450952>
- Adelino, M., Ma, S., & Robinson, D. (2017). Firm Age, Investment Opportunities, and Job Creation. *The Journal of the American Finance Association*, 999-1038.
- Adiandari, A., & Winata, H. (2020). MSME sector financial inclusion through optimal pick-up services. *Journal of Management and Business Studies*, 7(2), 119-125.
- Ananda, A.D., Susilowati, D. (2017). *Pengembangan Usaha Mikro Kecil dan Menengah. Berbasis Industri Kreatif di Kota Malang*. *Jurnal Ilmu Ekonomi X (X)*.
- Aritonang, M., Sadalia, I., & Muluk, C. (2023). The Effect of Financial Literacy and Financial Inclusion on MSMEs Performance. *AEBMR*, 356-368. doi:https://doi.org/10.2991/978-94-6463-008-4_46
- Atnafu, D., & Balda, A. (2018). The impact of inventory management practice on firms' competitiveness and organizational performance: Empirical evidence from micro and small enterprises in Ethiopia. *Cogent Business & Management*.
- Banerjee, R., Maruta, A., & Donato, R. (2022). Does higher financial inclusion lead to better health outcomes? Evidence from developing and transitional economies. *Economics of Transition and Institutional Change*, 363-401. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/ecot.12341>
- Barajas, A., Beck, T., Belhaj, M., & Naceur, S. (2020). Financial Inclusion: What Have We Learned So Far? What Do We Have to Learn? *International Monetary Fund*, 51. doi:<https://doi.org/10.5089/9781513553009.001>
- Beck, T. (2016, November 21). *Financial Inclusion – measuring progress and progress in measuring*. Retrieved from International

Monetary Fund: https://www.imf.org/external/np/seminars/eng/2016/statsforum/pdf/beck_paper.pdf

Bhandari, P. (2023, June 2022). Correlational Research | When & How to Use. Retrieved from Scribbr: <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/correlational-research/>

Bhaskar, P. V. (2013). Non-Banking Finance Companies: Game Changers.

Camara, N., & Tuesta, D. (2014). Measuring Financial Inclusion: A Multidimensional Index. BBVA Research

Cavalchire, J. (2023, March 10). Why Banking Relationships Matter. Retrieved from LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/why-banking-relationships-matter-joe-cavalchire>

Centobelli, P., Cerchione, R., Esposito, E., Passaro, R., & Shashi. (2021). Determinants of the transition towards circular economy in SMEs: A sustainable supply chain management perspective. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 242. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2021.108297>

Cole, S., Gine, X., Tobacman, J., Topalova, P., Townsend, R., & Vickery, J. (2013). Barriers to Household Risk Management: Evidence from India. *American Economic Journal: Applied Economics*, 104-135.

Covin, J. G., Green, K. M., & Slevin, D. P. (2013). *Entrepreneurship Theory And Practice*.

Dewinta, I., & Setiawan, P. (2016). The Influence Of Company Size, Company Age, Profitability, Leverage, And Sales Growth On Tax Avoidance. *Accounting E-Journal*, 1584-1615.

Fiala, N. (2015). Access to Finance and Enterprise growth: Evidence from an experiment in Uganda. International Labor Organization.

Fundid. (2023, August 1). How to use a Small Business Loan to Hire Employees. Retrieved from getfundid: <https://www.getfundid.com/loans/how-to-use-a-small-business-loan-to-hire-employees>

Gammage, S., Kes, A., Winograd, L., Sultana, N., Hiller, S., & Bourgault, S. (2017). Gender and digital financial inclusion: What do we know and what do we need to know? International Centre for Research on Women (ICRW).

Hutabarat, F. (2018). The Influence of Finance and Financial Literacy Technology towards Community Financial Inclusion. Bogor Agricultural Institute, 1-55.

Indra, A., Wibowo, B., Sembiring, S., & Metalia, M. (2020). The Effect of Profitability and Growth on Micro Small and Medium Enterprise (MSME) Capital Structure with The Size of The Company as a Control Variable. ICEBE. doi:10.4108/eai.1-10-2020.2305573

Irman, M., Budiyanto, & Suwitho. (2021). Increasing Financial Inclusion Through Financial Literacy and Financial Tchnology on MSMEs. *International Journal of Economics Development Research*, 126-141.

Kassa, E. (2021). Socioeconomic determinants of micro and small enterprise growth in North Wollo and Waghimira Zone selected towns. *Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship*. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13731-021-00165-5>

Lakuma, C., Marty, R., & Muhumuza, F. (2019). Financial inclusion and micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs) growth in Uganda. *Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship*. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13731-019-0110-2>

Lekhanya, L. M. (2016). "Business characteristics of small and medium enterprises in rural areas: a case study on southern region of KwaZulu-Natal province of South Africa. *Problems and Perspectives in Management*, 108-114. doi:[http://dx.doi.org/10.21511/ppm.14\(3\).2016.11](http://dx.doi.org/10.21511/ppm.14(3).2016.11)

Lim, J., Aquino, J., Garcia, J., Ong, R., & Soliman, D. (2020). The Impact of Demand Side Barriers and Supply Side barriers to Financial Inclusions: A Study on Micro Enterprises in Metro Manila. *Review of Integrative Business and Economics Research*, 9(3)

Lumenta, U., & Worang, F. (2019). The Influence of Financial Inclusion on the Performance of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises in North Sulawesi. *Jurnal EMBA*, 2910-2918.

Maravelle, A., & Pandiella, A. G. (2022). Expanding access to finance to boost growth and reduce inequalities. The Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) Library.

Marchese, M., & de la Chaux, M. (2022). MSME Productivity, Inclusive Growth and Decent Work Creation. The Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) Library.

Mutantabowa, B. (2018). The Impact Of Financial Literacy On The Success And Profitability (Performance) Of Small And Medium Enterprises In Lusaka Central Business District (Doctoral dissertation, Cavendish University).

Ngoc, N., Tien, N., Chau, P., & Khuyen, T. (2021). The Impact Of Capital Structure On Business Performance Of Real Estate Enterprise Listed At Ho Chi Minh City Stock Exchange. *PalArch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt/Egyptology*.

- Oke, D., Soetan, R., & Ayedun, T. (2023). Financial Inclusion and the Performance of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises in Southwest Nigeria. 29th RSEP International Conference on Economics, Finance & Business . doi:<https://doi.org/10.19275/RSEPCONFERENCES239>
- Opperman, P. (2023). Financial inclusion and performance of MSMEs in Eswatini. *International Journal of Social Economics*. doi:10.1108/IJSE-10-2020-0689
- Overman, H. (2016, June). Evidence topic: Access to finance. Retrieved from [whatworksgrowth: https://whatworksgrowth.org/resource-library/access-to-finance/](https://whatworksgrowth.org/resource-library/access-to-finance/)
- Pomeroy, R., Arango, C., Lomboy, C., & Box, S. (2020). Financial inclusion to build economic resilience in small-scale fisheries. *Marine Policy*. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2020.103982>
- Raquiza, M. V. (2021). Micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSME) sector financing issues and challenges. University Of The Philippines Center For Integrative And Development Studies. doi:ISSN 2619-7456
- Siedlecki, S. (2020). Understanding Descriptive Research Designs and Methods. *Research Gate*, 8-12. doi:10.1097/NUR.0000000000000493
- Stangor, C. (2014). Psychologists Use Descriptive, Correlational, and Experimental Research Designs to Understand Behaviour. Retrieved from PressBooks: <https://opentextbc.ca/introductiontopsychology/chapter/2-2-psychologists-use-descriptive-correlational-and-experimental-research-designs-to-understand-behavior/>
- Suryani, T., Lindiwati, & Iramani, R. (2015). The Challenge Of Financial Inclusion For Small And Micro Entreprises In Indonesia. *International Journal of Social Sciences*, 1076-1087.
- Tambunan, E., Enuh, K., Ubaidullah, & Tamba, M. (2022). Capital Access For Micro Small Medium Enterprises. *Jurnal Ekonomi dan Perbankan Syariah*, 148-158.
- Ton, Z., & Raman, A. (2015). The Effect of Product Variety and Inventory Levels on Retail Store Sales: A Longitudinal Study. *Production And Operations Management*.
- Wijaya, R., & Hartini, F. (2022). The Role of Financial Inclusion in Improving Community Welfare: A Study on Cooperative Business. *European Union Digital Library*. doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.4108/eai.3-8-2021.2315152>
- Xiao, J., Huang, J., Goyal, K., & Kumar, S. (2022). Financial Capability: A Systematic Conceptual Review, Extension, and Synthesis. *Human Development and Family Science Faculty Publications*. doi:<https://doi/10.1108/IJBM-05-2022-0185>
- Zigraiova, D., & Tomas, H. (2015). Bank Competition and Financial Stability: Much Ado About Nothing? *Institute of Economic Studies*.

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Sarah Jane B. Orillosa, DBM

Notre Dame of Midsayap College – Philippines

Camille George R. Olarte

Notre Dame of Midsayap College – Philippines

Hana Khrystelle A. Cariño

Notre Dame of Midsayap College – Philippines

Christ Stephen C. Halog

Notre Dame of Midsayap College – Philippines

Allea Angelica N. Chua

Notre Dame of Midsayap College – Philippines

Justine Noel L. Dasas

Notre Dame of Midsayap College – Philippines

Jerome C. Orillosa, CPA, DBM

Notre Dame of Midsayap College – Philippines